

Identification of management development needs: a comparison across companies of different ownership: Foreign, joint-venture and local in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of an empirical investigation of 78 human resource managers employed in 78 wholly foreign owned, foreign and local joint venture and wholly local owned export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. The study investigated human resource managers' views on whether organisations identify development needs of managers, and if so, from what sources. The findings of the study shed light on the identification of management development needs and on differences across companies of different ownership. The data revealed evidence of the existence of the identification of development needs of managers in the industry. Organisational strategies, succession plans and performance appraisal give rise to identify development needs of managers, other than requests from both heads of divisions/immediate superior managers who like their subordinates to be developed and managers themselves who desire to develop. Further, the results of the analysis of variance revealed that in certain aspects there are significant differences in the identification of development needs of managers. The results and implications of the findings are discussed.

KEY WORDS: Clothing industry, Management development, Needs identification, Sri Lanka

INTRODUCTION

Development needs identification is a process of information gathering to diagnose changing requirements of the organisation and people in it to cater both present and future organisational needs by turning them into development requirements. Development needs identification should follow a logical sequence, starting from an assessment of the overall company trajectory and its

future plans, down through the implications of these plans for sectional skill needs, and then on to the individual development needs.

There is a compelling logic to this three-tiered approach (organisation, job and person) and reflects view of both the organisation and managers within it (Esterby-Smith and Ashton, 1979; Mole, 2000; Stewart, 1994; Wills, 1998). First, organisational strategies and policies are the ‘umbrella’ under which individual and organisational MD needs are identified and form the boundaries within which MD should take place (Mathis and Jackson, 1994; Wills, 1998).

Second, the department/division’s mission and the work processes an organisation uses determine jobs the department/division needs to accomplish organisational objectives.

Documented information of performance appraisal, succession plans, departmental purpose, objectives and policies, departmental processes/systems, group outcomes, quality control reports, etc give rise to identify MD needs in this regard (Mathis and Jackson, 1994; Wills, 1998; Bratton and Gold, 1999; Mumford et al. 1987). Finally, the individual requirements give a picture of the demand within a department but not necessarily the need (Wills, 1998). Fulfilment of such needs maximise the contribution from the managers to the company and on the other enables them to maximise their personal development (Bagshaw, 1996). Only by an identification of MD needs, MD programmes could be designed in such a way that they are valuable experience for the learner, and fulfil the development requirements to operate and co-operate effectively in an organisational context.

The focus of this paper is on the discussion of results of an empirical investigation on whether organisations identify MD needs, and if so, from what sources. In this context, a number of

specific questions are examined. These include: Do companies identify MD needs? What are the sources of identifying MD needs? Do companies identify MD needs connected to organisational strategy? Do companies use information from succession plans in the identification of MD needs? Do companies use information from performance appraisal in the identification of MD needs? Do companies use sources, other than organisational strategy, succession plan and performance appraisal, in the identification of MD needs, such as requests made by managers themselves for their own development and requests made by heads of the divisions /immediate superior managers who like their subordinates to be developed? Though attention has been devoted to the comparison of HRM systems, to date there remains a dearth of empirical research conducted to address these in the Asian developing country context. Specifically, none of such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka, where business operations have been increasing and have a high profile. Within this context, the study set out to fill the gap in literature by comparing MD practices in the identification of development needs of managers across foreign, joint venture and local companies based on the assumption that there may be significant differences across companies of different ownership. This paper seek to answer the above questions by offering a brief description on the Sri Lankan context and then analysing the results of the survey conducted in Sri Lanka. The conclusions address the existing practice and implications.

SRI LANKAN CONTEXT AND MD NEEDS IDENTIFICATION

Sri Lanka had been under Western rule for several centuries and became independent in 1948. The country eventually followed the economic, political and administrative structures introduced by the British, which lasted over several centuries. In the pursuit of industrialisation, Sri Lanka is

left with few options to survive and thrive in a more complex and unpredictable global situation. With high unemployment and insufficient indigenous capital, the attraction of foreign investment becomes a major priority (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). On the other hand, in response to several factors such as increasing global competition, lower labour cost in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing since the introduction of open economic policies in 1977.

Export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry has become the leading manufacturing and export industry in Sri Lanka by 1990s. It has emerged to the position of the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector. Hence, policy makers have placed heavy emphasis on the industry as means of promoting employment and generating foreign exchange earnings by recognising it as the main contributor to the overall economic development (Senanayake, 2001). The impressive growth witnessed in the industry can be attributed to two major factors. The first factor is the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977 (Karunatilake, 1999). The second factor is the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA) that granted export quotas to developing countries like Sri Lanka, by guaranteeing export markets (Karunatilake, 1999; Senanayake, 2001). In the circumstances, the overseas manufacturers of clothing from both East Asia (such as, Hong Kong, Taiwan, South Korea and Singapore) and Europe (such as, Germany, UK) have relocated their production facilities to Sri Lanka and fuelled the growth of the industry. While the East Asian manufacturers have moved their operations mainly due to quota availability, European manufacturers have moved their operations due to rising production costs in their home countries (Karunatilake, 1999; Senanayake, 2001). At present, several export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies

operate in Sri Lanka as wholly local owned companies (local), wholly foreign owned companies (foreign) or as foreign and local joint venture companies (joint venture).

On the other hand, apart from the contribution made by joint venture and foreign companies to the economic growth of the country, it is suggested that attitudes to human resource are somewhat different in the foreign companies; they have started to develop human resource having identified it as a key to improvements in the industry (Gunawardana, 1999; Tennekoon, 1998). Further, it is an accepted fact in Sri Lanka that human resource has and will continue to play a significant role in the global competition. Therefore, on one hand, Sri Lankan government has been taking steps to enhance industry relevant employee skills to attract foreign investment. On the other hand, local entrepreneurs have recognised that the availability of high quality managers, in fact, places organisations at a competitive advantage over others even within the same industry, have taken concrete measures to provide organise HRD programmes in their organisations and to bring in human resource personnel to the corporate management (Dept. of National Planning, 1992; Jayaratna, 1996).

METHODOLOGY

Population and sample

The export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies registered under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) served as the population of the study for several reasons. First, BOI is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country (BOI, a) and export-oriented clothing manufacturing is the major industrial category under BOI (BOI, a). Second, it is compulsory by law that all

foreign investments (wholly foreign owned and foreign/local joint venture) should come into the country through BOI (BOI, a; BOI, b). Therefore, this provides easy and systematic access to foreign invested companies. Third, it is compulsory by law that all BOI registered companies should export at least 90 percent of the manufactured output (BOI, a; BOI, b). Thus, all local, foreign and joint venture companies that come under this study population are homogeneous in nature in terms of business operations.

At the time of the study, there were 207 (82 local, 68 foreign, 57 joint venture) export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies registered under BOI. It is decided to select a proportionate stratified random sample of 100 companies based on the ownership. In selecting a sample of 100 companies, initial contacts were made over the telephone using the simple random sample method within each strata until the required number of companies, for each strata, agree to participate in the study. However, due to various reasons the total number of companies that agreed to participate in the study amounted to 78 (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture) out of 100. However, this is a very high response rate especially within the Sri Lankan context. The number of companies in each category of the sample (local, foreign, joint venture) consisted of more than 35 per cent of the companies in the each category of the population. Of the companies that had responded to the study, 41 per cent of the companies in the sample were locally owned. This means that 59 per cent of the companies in the randomly selected sample comprised of foreign owned and joint venture companies. With regard to the number of managers employed in the companies, 59 per cent of the companies have employed more than 10 managers and 26 per cent of the companies have employed 6 to 10 managers. With regard to the number of employees in the companies, 46 per cent of the companies have employed 101 to 500 employees, 33 per

cent of the companies have employed 501 to 1000 employees, and 18 per cent of the companies have employed more than 1000 employees. 51 per cent of the companies have separate HRD units/departments.

Methods of data collection

The data was collected through questionnaire and structured interviews in order to capture the dimensions of the investigation. It is anticipated that the results of the questionnaire may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Questionnaire was constructed by the researcher as unable to find any survey conducted in Sri Lanka that has slight resembleness to the study. The preliminary investigations of the researcher gave insight into the HR practices within the industry. To collect necessary information in a manner that puts the least burden on expected respondents, information that could be accessible from other sources, such as interviews was excluded from the self-administered questionnaire. Questions in the self-administered questionnaire took the form of closed ended questions in a Likert-scale as they have proven themselves to be more efficient and ultimately more reliable. The questionnaire was pilot tested to improve the reliability and face validity of the instrument. As the study looked into organisational practices of MD needs identification, questionnaire was designed and administrated to human resource (HR) managers. The survey questionnaire relevant to the identification of MD needs covered five aspects as listed bellow:

- Existence of MD needs identification
- Assistance given by organisational strategy- the identification of compulsory MD needs and identification of new needs to be compatible with business needs

- Assistance given by succession plans- the existence of succession plans and usage of succession planning information to identify needs
- Assistance given by performance appraisal- the existence of performance appraisal and usage of performance appraisal information to identify needs
- Assistance given by requests- requests from managers themselves for their own development and requests made by heads of divisions/immediate superior managers who like their subordinates to be developed

Interviews were deemed necessary to complement the survey questionnaire to corroborate the information that had been gathered from the survey questionnaires and to elaborate the field by exploring a greater variety of experiences offered by HR managers. It was decided to conduct interviews after the preliminary analysis of data obtained from self-administered questionnaire for two reasons. First, the answers to the survey questionnaire may provide the researcher some new insights, which should be further investigated. Second, if the researcher had found out something, which should have been asked but omitted in the questionnaires, then during the interviews those areas can be dealt with. The interviews are structured along the outline topics with open questions. The main content of interview guide as listed bellow:

- Documentation of MD needs during the performance appraisal
- Usage of performance appraisal information in identifying MD needs
- Documentation of MD needs during the performance appraisal
- Usage of succession planning information in identifying MD needs

- Reactions to requests received formally/informally from managers/managers' immediate superiors

There were no problems in selecting the sample of HR managers, as there is only one HR manager per each randomly selected company. 78 HR managers (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture) from the stratified randomly selected sample responded to the questionnaire. 18 HR managers (7 local, 6 foreign, 5 joint venture) from the stratified randomly selected sample willingly agreed to participate in the interviews. The classification of the HR managers' sample is shown in table 1.

INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Information on the demographics of the sample is shown in table 2.

INSERT TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE

RESULTS

Identification of MD needs

One of the objectives of the study highlighted earlier is to investigate whether MD needs are identified in the industry. 59 per cent of the companies frequently identify MD needs ($x=3.56$). However, only about 4 per cent of the companies do not identify MD needs frequently. The reason such companies revealed is that they recruit only qualified personnel for jobs as they could not afford to provide development programmes due to reasons, such as lack of time and

lack of personnel to substitute managers those who would be released for MD programmes. Thus, companies expect managers to be equipped with required knowledge, skills and abilities at the time of recruitment. These companies advertise vacancies through newspapers and select candidates on a competitive basis, paying salaries at sufficiently high level to recruit and retain personnel of the required standard. Where further development is required, it is most often left to the initiative of the individual employee, who may be encouraged by prospects of a promotion or salary increment to undertake MD programmes, off-the-job, relating to the field of employment on his/her own expense (time and/or money). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) performed at the significant level of 0.05 indicates that there are significant differences in the identification of MD needs (table 3). Further analysis of Least Significant Differences (LSD) shows that joint venture companies are more likely to identify MD needs than that of local companies. The mean values given in table 3 also indicate this.

INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE

Several aspects relating to MD needs identification have been revealed during the interviews. Almost all companies have emphasised identifying MD needs in relation to technical aspects of jobs. In such instances, these companies have given more weight in developing lower and middle level managers in technical areas of clothing manufacturing. Some of such popular technical fields are work study, maintenance, quality assurance, and international standards on quality management (ISO 9000 and ISO 14000). In addition to technical skills, business communication skills of managers have also been identified as the next most vital need. Other than these, most of the companies have emphasised the need of identifying behavioural skill needs of managers,

irrespective of their type of ownership. Most of such companies have emphasised the need of developing leaders, especially, at the middle level. As the majority of supervisors (lower level) come from operative level workers, companies find that their behavioural abilities are lacking opposed to knowledge and skills they possess to become supervisors. It is, further, revealed that this trend of identifying MD needs on behavioural aspects is new to the industry and provision of programmes to fulfil such needs have become popular due to the changing scenario of the industry. It is prominent that one joint venture company classify MD needs into three categories, namely technical skills, management skills and future skills needs and the company identifies these MD needs in relation to all managers, irrespective of their level in the company (lower/middle/top).

Overall, data obtained from both questionnaires and interviews give evidence to the existence of MD needs identification in the industry. The evidence supports observations made by other Sri Lankan researchers, though none of the studies were conducted in the export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry, that there is evidence for the existence of MD needs identification in Sri Lankan organisations (Fonseka, 1998; Silveira, 2000; Sivanesan, 2000; Wijetunge, 1992).

The assistance given by the organisational strategy in identifying MD needs

76 per cent of the companies have organisational strategies. However, these findings are not consistent with earlier studies conducted in the Sri Lankan context by Nanayakkara (1992), Sivanesan (2000), Wijesiriwardana (1994) and Wijetunge (1992), who found that strategy making was not considered as a pre-requisite to success. However, it is worth noting that any of these studies were not conducted in the industry concerned. Though data reveal that the majority

of companies do have organisational strategies, considerable number of companies affirmed that they have unwritten strategies implying considerable degree of scope and opportunity to develop a strategic dimension to their businesses.

Data analysis revealed that the identification of MD needs to address specific company issues is the most popular (53%, $x=3.52$) while the existence of the identification of MD needs before being given promotions is the second most popular (31%, $x=3.04$). However, only 20 per cent ($x=2.62$) of the companies identify MD needs before being given salary increments. The identification of compulsory MD needs just after recruitment to a managerial position (29%, $x=2.95$) and after a certain period of service at the managerial level (22%, $x=2.66$) are also practised in the industry to a certain extent. ANOVA performed at the significant level of 0.05 indicates that there are no significant differences in four out of five aspects from which MD needs could be identified across companies (table 4). However there are significant differences in the identification of MD needs just after recruited to a managerial position. Further analysis of LSD show that both foreign and joint venture companies are more likely to identify MD needs just after recruited to a managerial position than that of local companies.

INSERT TABLE 4 ABOUT HERE

During the interviews it is revealed that that companies identify MD needs to address specific company issues at three levels, i.e., at the reactive level, to upgrade existing systems in order to survive and to address possible future needs. The majority of companies identify MD needs at the reactive level, i.e., after a problem/deficiency has been identified. Companies also identify MD needs in order to upgrade existing systems of work based on the current trends in quality

assurance procedures, information technology, import and export procedures, manufacturing technology, etc. Fulfilling MD needs at this level is now common procedure in many countries (Avery et al. 1999; Glover and Siu, 2000; Smith and Hayton, 1999). However, the scope of these programmes may be limited to meeting development requirements of enterprises only at the most general level (Smith and Hayton, 1999). In the case of new technology, companies identify MD needs connected to new forms of product and process technology, especially, in the manufacturing function. When new products (garments) are introduced, MD needs are identified relating to all lower level managers to manufacture these products. Thus, investigations revealed that these development requirements are relatively routine and fulfilled by means of on-the-job programmes. New processes, however, involve fundamental changes to the way in which work is carried out. For example, an introduction of new Accounting packages. Therefore, new processes give rise to identify more extensive MD needs within a company. Other than these, few companies have taken steps to identify new MD needs to address future requirements, which depends on company's business interests and on the predictions of how the industry will be moving in the future. HR manager from a joint venture company explained:

“Sometimes we introduce new development items to address expected future needs of the company. Those are especially for lower level and middle level managers. We look at them from the point of view how industry will be moving during next five years, company's business interests and how company expect to move during the next coming years.”

(interview)

With regard to the identification of compulsory MD needs just after recruited to a managerial position, companies identify these for newly recruited managers in the production function than any other function within the company. Further investigations revealed that these are fulfilled by

providing compulsory induction programmes by means of job rotation to give an overall perspective of all the aspects of the production function. However, the duration of compulsory induction programmes varies in a range of six months to one year, from one company to another. After the completion of initial compulsory programmes, specific MD needs are identified in relation to the posts in which newly recruited managers for the production function will be confirmed. HR manager from a foreign company revealed:

“After recruited, job rotation is a must during the 9 months of the probation period. After 9 months, the person is confirmed in a managerial post and is given relevant specific programmes to that confirmed position. If required, we provide further development opportunities and those depend on the job performance”.

(interview)

However, majority of companies do not identify MD needs of newly recruited managers. Such companies find it costly to provide MD programmes just after the recruitment as there is a tendency that managers leave the company in search of better jobs during the probationary/management trainee period. However, it is difficult to agree with this reason and find it as an excuse for not identifying MD needs at this level as there is no bond/agreement between company and managers even after he/she is confirmed in a managerial position. Hence, they can leave the company at anytime even though companies fulfilled MD needs after they are confirmed in the managerial positions, after completing probationary/management trainee period. Therefore, this situation can be seen as the use of probation/management trainee period as a substitute for MD. This situation could have led to find, in table 4, significant differences in this aspect across companies.

With regard to the identification of MD needs before being given promotions, companies revealed that it is a pre-requisite and condition to identify MD needs of lower and middle level managers through performance appraisal and fulfil those needs before been promoted to the next position. However, some other companies revealed that there are prescribed MD programmes to be completed by the identified candidate for the promotion to prepare that person for the higher post. However, the applicability of such prescribed programmes have to be taken into account cautiously as managers could be provided with these year after year not because of the value of the programme for development but completion is a prerequisite in giving promotions (Clarke and Matalina, 2000).

Identification of MD needs connected to succession plans

The data revealed that exactly half of the sample (39 companies=50%) maintains succession plans while the other half does not. Though human resource personnel hold the main responsibility in maintaining succession plans, it is accepted that a contribution should also be made by the heads of divisions in creating and maintaining succession plans. HR manager from a joint venture company explained:

“All heads of divisions have been asked to develop a succession plan for the people in their divisions. A vacuum should not be created. Someone should be able to fill the vacancy and take over the work smoothly. What we told is, if they had not created a successor, they wouldn't get promoted”.

(interview)

Such companies have recognised the value of identifying potential successors as early as possible so as to develop suitable MD programmes for them. This finding does not consistent with the findings of Wijesiriwardana (1994), which show that not even least effort is taken by the

Sri Lankan private sector organisations to maintain succession plans; direct recruitment is preferred. However, Wijesiriwardana's study (1994) was not conducted in the industry concerned. HR managers from the companies that do not maintain succession plans revealed that succession plans might be difficult to administer and could create conflicts if one person is selected in advance as a potential for a promotion. HR manager from a joint venture company revealed:

“Succession plan will be helpful in identifying MD needs. But practically it is very difficult to create and maintain. Succession plan could create problems like conflicting interests, when others come to know that ‘this’ person has been identified to take up a higher position”.

(interview)

Another reason revealed for not having succession plans is difficulties created due to high mobility of managers. There are vast job opportunities available for experienced managers within the industry. Sri Lankan managerial labour market, like UK, is highly segmented (Storey et al, 1997). A manager begins his/her career in a function, such as accountancy, engineering, marketing or HRM, which has its own professional body, entry qualifications, codes of ethics and discipline. Therefore, it is difficult for individual managers to acquire experience from promotion and mobility within the organisation rather than from moving between different organisations. Hence, it could be said that career mobility reflected to be a common occurrence among Sri Lankan professionals. In this regard, a production manager interviewed described how work experience and mobility helped him to reach higher and higher positions in hierarchies of different organisations, during a period of 12 years.

“I joined the industry as a production assistant in a local clothing company. It was 1988. I worked there for 4 years. During that time I completed a course on

clothing manufacturing (using own funds). Then I joined another company as an assistant quality control manager. I was given much better remuneration there. I worked there for nearly 2 years. My experience with the first and second jobs helped me to get my third job in a buying office- it is a foreign one. I got lot of experience in handling (including shipping) many world-reputed brands. After about 5 years, I joined my 4th job (current job) as the production manager. It is also a local company. This place was in search of a person who can handle Marks & Spencer orders; I got that experience from my 3rd job. Now my basic salary is 1 ½ times more than my 3rd job”.

(interview)

In this regard, the majority of export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies considers it as an achievement to grab a professional manager from another export-oriented clothing manufacturing company, encouraging further career mobility. Such companies view it as an opportunity to acquire knowledge, skills, abilities, organisational secrets, etc, the manager brings in from the out side.

Due to lot of job opportunities available in the industry at competitive remuneration, companies have recognised that it is difficult to retain good performers unless promotion system is not available. Therefore, though senior managerial positions are excluded from the internal promotion systems by the companies that do not have succession plans, middle and lower level managers are identified as potential successors. According to one HR manager from a local company:

“From the performance on the job we promptly recognise and promote high-performers. Otherwise, he/she will be taken by another company. All companies have similar divisions and positions; always have vacant jobs. So we are very careful. If good performers leave, it is difficult for us to replace them. ”

(interview)

Such companies accept that if a vacancy is identified, at least few months before, or if new positions are going to be created, HR managers are encouraged to look for a person inside based on performance appraisal information and to identify MD needs to provide them with necessary MD programmes before and/or after the appointment.

Thus, internal promotions given by companies that do not maintain succession plans prefer to promote operational level workers to lower level management and lower level managers to middle level management, as they can better understand the prevailing company system of “doing things”. Such internal succession provides continuity, stability and promotes loyalty. As internal candidates have developed the existing corporate strategy with incumbent management, they are not likely to disrupt current strategies, corporate culture and control structure (Lauterbach and Weisberg, 1994). On the other hand, proponents of external succession suggest that external succession can achieve more drastic changes in a company because externally recruited managers are not bound by old policies and implicit contracts within a company (Fields et al. 2000). In this context, the prevalent system in these companies creates doubts on to what extent externally recruited senior managers are capable of transforming the existing way of doing things, if the grass root level prefers the otherwise.

Results for the investigation on the usage of information from succession plans to identify MD needs of potential management successors revealed that out of the 39 companies that maintain succession plans, 64 per cent use them to identify MD needs of potential successors. ANOVA performed at the significant level of 0.05 indicates that there are significant differences in the

usage of information from succession plans in the identification of MD needs (table 5). Further analysis of LSD shows that joint venture companies are more likely to use information from succession plans to identify MD needs than that of local companies. The mean values given in table 5 also indicate this.

INSERT TABLE 5 ABOUT HERE

Identification of MD needs connected to performance

The data revealed that 99 per cent of the companies have formal systems of appraising managerial performance. Only one local company, which was initially established as a family owned business with family members in the managerial posts, is reluctant to appraise performance of managers. The majority of companies (93%) appraise performance of managers at least once a year. This finding is consistent with the other studies conducted in Sri Lanka by Dias (1990) and Chandratilake (1997) although those studies were not conducted in the industry concerned.

The majority of the companies have written documents on procedures and guidelines for performance appraisal which centres on performance appraisal forms. Such documents revealed the extent to which companies make effort to standardise the practices of performance appraisal of managers throughout organisations. Performance targets are stated in the appraisal form, where each and every company uses its own grading system that use objective-based rating and/or ranking techniques. However, in all cases emphasis is placed on individual managers' performance. Further, appraisal system tend to rely on homogeneous, job based, results oriented

and essentially individualised criteria at all the levels of management. In the case of managers working in the production function related fields, performance appraisal is more focused on short-term criteria that hinder reduce costs, economise on wastage, reduce shipment delays, reduce rejection rates by the buyers, increase the number of pieces produced on daily or weekly basis, etc. In the case of behavioural aspects, emphasis is given to reduce the number of complaints received from production-floor workers, reduce daily absentees and monthly worker turnover, etc. When it comes to focus on long-term goals, especially, senior managers are given targets on three general categories: strategic accountabilities, job responsibilities, and development and special objectives. This fact also complies with the findings of Hsu and Leat (2000), where they observed usage of short as well as long-term criteria for assessment.

Companies also try to balance both qualitative and quantitative aspects in appraisal. Companies emphasise on having more qualitative aspects for managers at the higher levels of the hierarchy while more quantitative aspects for managers at the lower levels of the hierarchy. It is generally practised that immediate superior manager appraising the immediate subordinate managers; this is practised at the each level of the management. Snape et al (1998) also described the role of the immediate superior in the performance appraisal. During the appraisal interviews MD needs are identified other than setting targets for the next review period. This situation indicates that companies maintain a continuing agenda through regular meetings to ensure that progress is being made towards achieving the objectives agreed for each key result area. In some companies, as part of the appraisal process, managers are asked to write a report- on annual basis. In such reports, managers have to state their contribution to the company during the year and they can also point-out any development requirements that they might think will influence their current and/or future performance. These reports are discussed during the appraisal interview and then

transferred to his/her personal file. Eastby-Smith et al (1995) also observed the practice of written self-evaluation reports in their study. Submission of such reports emphasises self-evaluations and gives managers a feeling of democracy in an organisation. However, in the case of managers employed in the production function, other than the formal appraisals, informal appraisals also take place. Generally, progress on the production-floor is accounted for at least once a month during company progress review meetings, in which all the managers of the production function and the top management of the companies take part. During these review meetings, achievement of pre-set monthly production targets is highly evaluated. Hence, these informal appraisals could make a great influence on the survival of managers attached to the production function and on the identification of MD needs. HR managers held a view that performance appraisals- both formal and informal- are vital for the companies to remain in the competition within the country as well as within the world. However, it is felt that due to existing pressures on the managers employed in the production function to achieve production related targets, conflicts could arise between organisational and individual development interests. Organisational goals could lead to the creation of an adversarial, low-trust relationship between superiors and subordinates. This in turn precludes superior from performing a problem-solving and helper role that is essential if organisations want to serve developmental goals.

Results for the investigation on the usage of information from performance appraisal revealed that almost 67 per cent of the companies use them to identify current performance deficiencies, while 44 per cent of the companies use them to identify future MD needs. ANOVA performed at the significant level of 0.05 indicates that there are no significant differences in the identification

of both current and future MD needs based on performance appraisal information across companies - local, foreign and joint venture (table 6).

INSERT TABLE 6 ABOUT HERE

Identification of MD needs through “requests”

In the study, an attempt was made to investigate sources companies use other than organisational strategy, succession plans and performance appraisal to identify MD needs. The preliminary investigations of the study revealed that the requests are the most popular in this regard. Those are the requests made by managers themselves for their own development and requests made by heads of the divisions/immediate superior managers who like their subordinates to be developed.

The data revealed that 45 percent of the requests come from heads of the divisions /immediate superior managers, who like their management subordinates to be developed. 26 per cent of the requests come from managers themselves. These figures indicate that the companies also rely on individuals and their bosses to flag MD needs. Smith and Hayton (1999) also revealed similar results in their study. ANOVA performed at the significant level of 0.05 indicates that there are no significant differences in the identification of MD needs based on requests across companies- local, foreign and joint venture (table 7).

INSERT TABLE 7 ABOUT HERE

Heads of the divisions/immediate superior managers are the people, who identify MD needs that are directly connected to jobs, in addition through performance appraisal; they make requests to HR managers. After validating the received requests, HR managers look for avenues to fulfil these identified needs. In this regard, companies classify requests into two- requests connected to company interests and requests connected to individual interests. If the identified needs are connected to company interests and have not been identified earlier through performance appraisal, organisational strategy or succession plans, companies make arrangements to fulfil such. Further, having identified new needs, the organisational records are updated. However, when the need is wholly an individual's, majority of companies leave it to the initiation of the individual manager to undergo relevant programmes on his/her own expense (time and/or money). However, there are few companies that are willing to pay at least half of the programme fee of the chosen external off-the-job programme on behalf of the manager, in addition to the provision of time-off from work to participate in the programme. On the other hand, there are some other companies that not only pay half of the programme fee and provide time-off but also provide the other half of the fee as a loan (without interest) to the individual managers with sufficient time to pay that back in instalments. HR manager from a local company explained:

“We analyse the requests. Though they are not connected to the company interests, still we pay 50% of the cost. We know these people have financial difficulties; we give them a loan to cover the other 50% too. But he/she has to pay that back in instalments”.

(interview)

This approach gives certain benefits to the company too as it blocks the avenues available for the manager to look for better prospects in other companies, just after completing the programme.

Therefore, the company can make use of the new knowledge/abilities, the manager gained, if they find it valuable in a later time.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This paper has based on an empirical investigation on whether companies identify MD needs, and if so, from what sources. The survey results indicate evidence for the existence of identification of MD needs. Organisational strategies, succession plans, performance appraisal, requests from both heads of divisions/immediate superior managers and managers themselves give rise to identify MD needs. ANOVA revealed that joint venture companies are more likely to identify MD needs than that of local companies. Joint venture companies are more likely to use information from succession plans in the identification of MD needs than that of local companies. However, ANOVA did not reveal significant differences in the usage of information from performance appraisal and requests in the identification of MD needs across companies.

The design of the study made it possible to generalise some of the findings in a broader perspective. Hence, findings have wider practical and theoretical implications for the practices of MD in Sri Lankan companies.

First, based on the results of the analysis, it could be assumed that joint venture companies have provided a supportive environment in which both partners are engaged in learning to create an effective organisational context than that of foreign companies. On the other hand, from the local companies' point of view, though the study found significant differences between joint venture

companies and local companies, local companies are not alien to prevalent practices. Local companies' familiarity to practices of MD needs identification could be attributed to two main reasons. One reason could be as the studies of Laburn (1994) and Lawler et al (1995) reveal the British colonial system had enormous influence on the management practices in Sri Lanka. The other reason could be business systems competing in world markets have to adapt to dominant patterns in those markets. Management concepts enter into the play in the forms of the requirements of foreign buyers and international standards. In this context, the findings seem to reveal that Sri Lanka is not detached from the rest of the world; they are also practising them to some extent. However, local companies have to better organise and communicate the elements of MD. The fundamental routes that prevail in the industry have to be strengthened.

Second, though Sri Lankan sample displays identification of MD needs based on individual managerial performance, none of the efforts have been revealed that have taken to use group measurement criteria in performance appraisals, which could induce co-operative and interdependent behaviour that results in improved performance. As companies identify MD needs connected to new forms of product and process technology, innovation in work organisations in terms of the introduction of teamwork with associated changes in job design, and workplace change in the form of the implementation of quality assurance strategies could lead to identify new MD needs in behavioural skills. These could involve fundamental changes to the way in which work is carried out.

Third, half of the companies of the sample do not maintain succession plans and revealed that succession plans might be difficult to administer and could create conflicts if one person is

selected in advance as a potential for a promotion. However, now, succession planning tries to balance pool of people against groups of jobs instead of trying to match individuals to particular positions through detailed plans (Lauterbach and Weisberg, 1994). Therefore, if attention is given to establish several promotional ladders for potentials at different levels, succession plan would not cause such problems. Instead, it would make an input to the strategy and develop managers with a long-term in mind. Such a flexible approach would increase the moral of potential successors.

However, few limitations of the study can also be identified. First, there are disadvantages of collecting survey data from one source (Ichniowski et al, 1996; Nichols, 1986). However, in the study, it was assumed that HR managers are the best people who can provide the relevant information on organisational practices of MD needs identification. Second, in the study, main emphasis was placed on identification of MD needs for which provision of formal aids are possible irrespective of the emerging trends in HRD. Hence, study had not reflected efforts that have taken to identify MD needs that can be fulfilled by formalising informal and accidental learning opportunities. Third, Hofstede (1993) has shown that the concepts of HR and HRD might be both country specific. Hence case studies or longitudinal studies could distinguish detailed country specific management practices, which could be tested for their underlying basic assumptions where those are different. Finally, since recruitment and retention dimensions of HRM strategy have not been investigated, the findings unable to provide information on whether companies view these approaches and MD complementary. These all opens door for further investigations.

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TABLES

Table 1: Classification of respondents

Instrument	Local	Foreign	Joint venture	Total
Survey questionnaire	32	26	20	78
Interview	7	6	5	18
Total	39	32	25	

Table 2: Sample composition

	%		%
<u>Age</u>		<u>Highest educational qualification</u>	
31 to 40 years	28	Diploma	55
41 to 50 years	56	Degree or equivalent	36
More than 50 years	15	Postgraduate degree	9
<u>Years of service in the present company</u>		<u>With professional qualification</u>	
5 years or less	41	Yes	64
6 to 10 years	47	No	36
More than 10 years	12		
		<u>Sex</u>	
		Male	81
		Female	19

Table 3: ANOVA of the identification of MD needs

Item	Mean			F	Sig.
	Local	Foreign	Joint venture		
MD needs identification	3.31	3.54	4.00	3.46	0.037

Table 4: ANOVA of the identification of MD needs connected to organisational strategy

Item	Mean			F	Sig.
	Local	Foreign	Joint venture		
Just after recruited to a managerial position	2.50	3.19	3.35	4.18	.019
After a certain period of service as a manager	2.45	2.60	3.05	1.73	.185
Before being given promotions	2.97	2.92	3.30	.878	.420
Before being given salary increments	2.41	2.60	3.00	1.84	.166
To address specific company issues	3.38	3.48	3.80	1.16	.320

Table 5: ANOVA of the usage of information from succession plans to identify MD needs

Succession planning information	Mean			F	Sig.
	Local	Foreign	Joint venture		
To identify MD needs of potential successors	3.21	3.79	4.45	6.22	.005

Table 6: ANOVA of the usage of information from performance appraisal to identify MD needs

Performance appraisal information	Mean			F	Sig.
	Local	Foreign	Joint venture		
To identify current needs	4.06	3.65	4.00	1.45	.242
To identify future needs	3.09	3.16	3.60	1.57	.515

Table 7: ANOVA of the identification of MD needs through requests

Requests	Mean			F	Sig.
	Local	Foreign	Joint venture		
From managers themselves	2.81	3.12	2.90	.706	.497
From heads of divisions/immediate superior managers	3.16	3.29	3.30	.135	.874